

PERCEPTIONS OF PROSPECTIVE YOUNG ENTREPRENEURS ON SUSTAINABLE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN BANDUNG CITY

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Abstract

This research aims to investigate the perceptions of prospective young entrepreneurs towards sustainable entrepreneurship in the city of Bandung. The study employs the Structural Equation Modeling - Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) method to analyze data obtained through the distribution of questionnaires to respondents who are prospective young entrepreneurs in Bandung. The findings of this research indicate that several factors influence the perceptions of prospective young entrepreneurs regarding sustainable entrepreneurship. Factors such as changing customer behavior, green marketing factors, favorable market conditions, and eco-friendly individuals may have a significant impact on how prospective young entrepreneurs assess the importance of sustainable entrepreneurship in the context of Bandung. This research makes a significant contribution to understanding the factors that influence the perceptions of prospective young entrepreneurs towards sustainable entrepreneurship in Bandung. The results of this study also provide deeper insights into how the concept of sustainable business can be more efficiently integrated into the context of Bandung, ultimately contributing to sustainable economic growth in Bandung and other cities in Indonesia.

Keywords: Perceptions of Sustainable Entrepreneurship, Changing Consumer Behavior, Green Marketing Factor, Favorable Market Conditions, and Eco-Friendly People.

1. INTRODUCTION

There have been new breakthroughs in Indonesia's academic landscape, with universities and institutes fostering innovation, exemplified by ventures like MyECO, a startup focused on efficiency founded by students. However, even as these products reach the market, they remain under university monitoring, revealing a gap in entrepreneurial perspectives within academia. Approximately 19% of Indonesians aged 25-34 with higher education degrees and only 8.4% of adults in Indonesia recognize business opportunities. This underscores the limited access to entrepreneurship training, hindering academics from acquiring essential skills and knowledge in business ventures. Consequently, there is a need to establish programs that strengthen sustainable business growth and connect students with mentors who can provide valuable business insights, thereby encouraging student and undergraduate entrepreneurship (CNBC Indonesia, 2023).

Eco-friendly businesses prioritize environmental aspects and aim to produce environmentally friendly products. Despite Indonesia's ranking as the 164th environmentally friendly country out of 180 in 2022, with a score of 28.20 points (Katadata, 2022), the government and BRI Bank have taken steps to boost entrepreneurship among the youth. Through programs like the People's Business Credit (KUR), which extends to campuses, the government aims to empower young entrepreneurs, especially students, by providing mentoring and training programs via BUMN housing facilities. These initiatives help business actors acquire new skills and

knowledge to expand their ventures. Additionally, students can access People's Business Credit (KUR) by obtaining a business certificate, with super micro KUR requiring IDR 10 million, micro KUR ranging from IDR 10 million to IDR 50 million, and small KUR necessitating capital between IDR 50 million and IDR 500 million (ekon.go.id). The government's support and training opportunities for entrepreneurial activities contribute to heightened awareness among graduating students about the importance of entrepreneurship in light of employment uncertainties (Demir & Demiryurek, 2018). Entrepreneurship training in universities not only fosters a propensity for students to initiate their ventures (Wang & Wong, 2004) but also influences their work preferences based on the knowledge gained (Tkachev & Kolvereid, 1999). Adekiya & Ibrahim (2016) posit a significant positive effect of both theoretical and practical entrepreneurship training on students' intentions toward entrepreneurship.

Sustainable entrepreneurship, as highlighted by Shepherd (2011), focuses on preserving nature, supporting life, and pursuing opportunities to realize the future of products, processes, and services while achieving profits (Adeline, F., & Slamet, 2021). It goes beyond creating products or services, emphasizing environmental responsibility and equality (Iwan Prasodjo and Rita Amelinda, 2019). The theory and application of sustainable entrepreneurship have gained attention, evolving from "business as usual" to the "double bottom line" and, currently, the "triple bottom line" (Lubis, R. L. 2022). To contribute to entrepreneurship, the Chairman of the Regional Leadership Council (DPD) of the Indonesian Islamic Da'wah Institute (LDII) in Bandung City emphasizes community participation in waste management, highlighting the economic value and potential as a community economic driver (Ldii Jabar, 2022). An alumnus of the Bandung Institute of Technology has exemplified this by establishing a startup that innovatively recycles agricultural waste into building materials. Utilizing sawdust, empty tandang, palm oil and sugarcane fiber dregs, and employing a natural adhesive derived from fungal mycelium, the startup produces decorative panels for interior wall elements and materials for journals, shoes, wallets, bags, and watches. This venture presents business opportunities for the development of sustainable entrepreneurship in Indonesia, particularly for Master's students majoring in business administration in Bandung City (Putri M. K. and Putri A. N., 2023).

Putri M. K. and Putri A. N. (2023) assert that entrepreneurial marketing plays a crucial role for small businesses facing challenges such as competition, limited information, market insight, product innovation deficiencies, capital constraints, and a lack of business skills and spiritual marketing. The application of entrepreneurial marketing becomes imperative for small businesses to compete effectively with other companies. Green marketing serves as a strategy for raising awareness of environmental conditions, encompassing various terms like environmental marketing, ecological marketing, sustainable marketing, greener marketing, and societal marketing. According to Nanere (2010), green marketing involves efforts to promote, produce, price, and develop products that do not harm the environment. Eva Nuriyah Hidayat (2021) defines green marketing as the marketing response to the environmental effects across the entire lifecycle of goods and services, including design, production, packaging, labeling, use, and disposal. In today's traditional market competition, green marketing extends beyond inclusive activities in packaging to modifying products and production processes that do not

harm the environment and meet customer needs (Bhatia M & Jain A 2014). Factors influencing the purchase of environmentally friendly products include consumer environmental values, attitudes, knowledge, product prices, and awareness (Schlegelmilch et al., 1996). Kim, N., & Lee, K. (2023) emphasize that environmental awareness plays a crucial role in bridging the gap between environmental issues and consumer behavior. Government participation and investments that subsidize sustainable entrepreneurship, coupled with market opportunities due to market failures (Dean and McMullen, 2007), have led to the creation of the National Economic Recovery (PEN) program. This program supports Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) through various financing forms, tax incentives, and cash assistance, facilitating favorable market conditions for entrepreneurial growth (ekon.go.id 2022). Jahanshahi et al. (2011) highlight a positive and significant relationship between entrepreneurial growth and government involvement. Therefore, government participation plays a pivotal role in creating favorable market conditions for entrepreneurship.

2. METHOD

This research uses quantitative research methods with descriptive and causal research objectives. In this study, researchers used variables which were divided into independent, dependent and moderating variables. In this study, researchers used non-probability sampling techniques. The researcher decided to use the technique of non-probability sampling in research because of the entire population, not all were sampled in the research. In this study, the number of master's students majoring in business administration in the city of Bandung is not known with certainty, so the sample size in this study was determined using the Slovin equation formula.

$$n = \frac{N}{[1+N(e^2)]}$$

Is known:

- n = Sample size
- N = Total population
- E = alpha (0.05) or 5% of the 95% confidence level is commonly used in research.

This research uses a confidence level of 95% so that a value of N = 1,469 Master of Business Administration students in Bandung City can be obtained and the error rate will be determined at 5%. The following are the results of sample calculations using the Lemeshow formula equation.

$$n = \frac{1.469}{[1+1.469(5\%^2)]}$$

n = 314

Based on the calculation above, the result shows 314.39, so the number of samples used in the research is 314.39, which is rounded up to 315 respondents. Based on this sample size, the minimum number of respondents required for this research is 315 respondents from Master's degree students majoring in business administration in the city of Bandung.

3. RESULT

3.1 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis is statistics used to analyze data by describing the collected data without intending to make general conclusions or generalizations (Sujaluet al., 2021). This descriptive statistical analysis aims to describe the opinions of 315 respondents regarding all variables. The following are the results of respondents' answers processed by researchers.

3.2 Descriptive Analysis Eco-Friendly People

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents' Answers Eco-friendly people

No	Statement Eco-friendly people	Alternative Answers					Shoes Total	Shoes Ideal	%	Category
		STS (1)	TS (2)	N (3)	S (4)	SS (5)				
1	I really love the environment	4	14	17	108	172	1375	1575	86%	Strongly agree
2	I am very interested in environmental activities such as planting trees	4	8	32	151	120	1320	1575	83%	Agree
3	I think that people are more conscious about the environment than ever before	5	15	62	133	100	1253	1575	79%	Agree
4	I turned off the lights wherever I deemed unnecessary, such as in the classroom	16	18	62	107	112	1226	1575	77%	Agree
5	I turn off the lights wherever I don't think it's necessary, like in the office	13	29	74	100	99	1188	1575	75%	Agree
6	I try to avoid using vehicles to carry goods (for example carrying milk in the morning) over very short distances	3	21	85	127	79	1203	1575	76%	Agree
Shoes Total									7565	
Shoes Ideal									9450	
Variable Average Eco – Friendly People									80%	

Source: (Author's Processed Data, 2023)

From the data results concerning the variable "eco-friendly people" in Table 4.1, the following descriptions can be provided:

1. I really love the environment:

Respondents overwhelmingly expressed their love for the environment, with 86% falling into the strongly agreed category. This suggests a strong affinity among respondents for the environment.

2. I am very interested in environmental activities such as planting trees:

Responses regarding interest in environmental activities, such as planting trees, showed 83% in the agree category. This indicates a significant level of interest among respondents in engaging in environmental activities like tree planting.

3. I think that people are more conscious about the environment than ever before:

A majority of respondents (79%) believe that people are now more environmentally conscious compared to the past. This demonstrates a prevailing perception among respondents that environmental awareness has increased.

4. I turn off the lights wherever I deem unnecessary, such as in the classroom:

Respondents demonstrated individual awareness by turning off lights in places like classrooms where unnecessary, with 77% agreeing to this behavior. This highlights a conscious effort among respondents to save energy.

5. I turn off the lights wherever I don't think it's necessary, like in the office:

Similarly, respondents (75%) expressed individual awareness by turning off lights in places like offices where deemed unnecessary. This reinforces the trend of conscious energy-saving practices.

6. I try to avoid using vehicles to carry goods (for example carrying milk in the morning) over very short distances:

A significant portion of respondents (76%) acknowledged attempting to minimize vehicle usage for short-distance transportation of goods, such as carrying milk in the morning. This indicates a conscious effort to reduce carbon footprint.

Considering the interpretation continuum line's score provisions, the average percentage for the variable "eco-friendly people" is 80%, falling within the agreed category range of 68% - 84%. Therefore, it can be concluded from this interpretation that individuals with eco-friendly behaviors influence perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship.

Figure 1: Eco – Friendly People Continuum Line

Source: (Author's Processed Data, 2023)

3.3 Descriptive Analysis Green Marketing Factors

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents' Answers Green Marketing Factors

No	Statement Green marketing factors	Alternative answer					Shoes total	Shoes ideal	%	Category
		STS (1)	TS (2)	N (3)	S (4)	SS (5)				
1	I know environmentally friendly products	4	16	18	123	154	1352	1575	85%	Strongly agree
2	I know about eco-friendly labeled products on the market	10	14	35	153	103	1270	1575	80%	Agree
3	Green products are initially more expensive than non-green products	6	18	41	145	105	1270	1575	80%	Agree
4	I feel there is a lack of eco-friendly products on the market	4	12	43	125	131	1312	1575	83%	Agree
5	Environmentally friendly products are a modern market demand	5	15	46	126	123	1292	1575	82%	Agree
6	Environmentally friendly products are a future demand for the market	3	12	42	121	137	1322	1575	83%	Agree
Shoes Total										7818
Shoes Ideal										9450
Variable Average Green Marketing Factors										82%

Source: (Author's Processed Data), 2023

From the data results concerning the variable "green marketing factors" in Table 4.2, the following descriptions can be provided:

1. I know environmentally friendly products:

Respondents overwhelmingly indicated their awareness of environmentally friendly products, with 85% falling into the strongly agreed category. This suggests a high level of knowledge among respondents regarding such products.

2. I know about eco-friendly labeled products on the market:

Responses regarding knowledge about environmentally friendly labeled products on the market showed 80% in the agree category. This indicates that respondents are familiar with eco-friendly labeled products available in the market.

3. Green products are initially more expensive than non-green products:

Respondents (80%) acknowledged that environmentally friendly products are initially more expensive than non-green products. This awareness reflects an understanding among respondents about the pricing dynamics of green products.

4. I feel there is a lack of eco-friendly products on the market:

A majority of respondents (83%) expressed a perception that there is a shortage of environmentally friendly products on the market. This highlights a sentiment among respondents that more eco-friendly options are needed.

5. Environmentally friendly products are a modern market demand:

Respondents (82%) agreed that environmentally friendly products represent a current market demand. This suggests an acknowledgment among respondents that there is a growing demand for eco-friendly products in the present market.

6. Environmentally friendly products are a future demand for the market:

A significant portion of respondents (83%) agreed that environmentally friendly products will be a future demand in the market. This indicates foresight among respondents, recognizing the anticipated increase in demand for eco-friendly products.

Considering the interpretation continuum line's score provisions, the average percentage for the variable "green marketing factors" is 82%, falling within the agreed category range of 68% - 84%. Therefore, based on the results of this interpretation, it can be concluded that green marketing factors significantly influence perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship.

Figure 2: Green Marketing Factors Continuum Line

Source: (Author's Processed Data, 2023)

3.4 Descriptive Analysis Changing Consumer Behavior

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Changing Consumer Behavior

No	Statement Changing consumer behavior	Alternative answer					Shoes total	Shoes ideal	%	Category
		STS (1)	TS (2)	N (3)	S (4)	SS (5)				
1	I buy products that can be recycled	10	20	43	124	118	1265	1575	80%	Agree
2	I try to avoid products that consume more energy	4	18	44	136	113	1281	1575	81%	Agree
3	I have a positive image of environmentally friendly products	4	16	42	140	113	1287	1575	81%	Agree
4	I realize as time changes my tastes change	9	15	41	135	115	1277	1575	81%	Agree

5	I realize as time changes my preferences change	8	12	60	114	121	1273	1575	80%	Agree
6	Environmental friendliness is my main concern when making purchasing decisions many times	6	17	54	106	132	1286	1575	81%	Agree
Shoes Total									7669	
Shoes Ideal									9450	
Variable Average Changing Consumer Behavior									81%	

Source: (Author's Processed Data, 2023)

From the results of data regarding variables Changing Consumer Behavior in table 4.3, it can be described as follows.

1. I buy products that can be recycled.

Respondents' responses about me buying products that can be recycled resulted in a percentage of 80% in the agree category. This indicates that respondents buy products that can be recycled.

2. I try to avoid products that consume more energy.

Respondents' responses about me trying to avoid products that consume more energy resulted in a percentage of 81% in the agree category. This means that respondents try to avoid products that consume more energy.

3. I have a positive image of environmentally friendly products.

Respondents' responses about me having a positive image of environmentally friendly products resulted in a percentage of 81% in the agree category. This indicates that respondents have a positive image of environmentally friendly products.

4. I realize as time changes my tastes change.

Respondents' responses about me realizing that changing times have changed my tastes resulted in a percentage of 81% in the agree category. This indicates that respondents are aware that as time changes my tastes change.

5. I realize as time changes my preferences change.

Respondents' responses about me realizing that over time my preferences have changed resulted in a percentage of 80% in the agree category. This indicates that respondents are aware that preferences change over time.

6. Environmental friendliness is my main concern when making purchasing decisions many times.

Respondents' responses about environmental friendliness are my main concern when making purchasing decisions, which repeatedly resulted in a percentage of 81% in the agree category. This indicates that respondents prioritize environmental friendliness when making purchasing decisions many times.

Based on the provisions of the score interpretation continuum line, it can be seen that the average percentage of the variable Changing Consumer Behavior was 81% with the agreed category being in the range of 68% - 84%. So it can be concluded based on the results of this interpretation Changing Consumer Behavior influences perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship.

Figure 3: Continuum Line of Changing Consumer Behavior

Source: (Author's Processed Data, 2023)

3.5 Descriptive Analysis Favourable Market Conditions

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Favorable Market Conditions

No	Statement Favorable market conditions	Alternative answer					Shoes total	Shoes ideal	%	Category
		STS (1)	TS (2)	N (3)	S (4)	SS (5)				
1	I can easily get a loan for my startup	6	14	34	124	137	1317	1575	83%	Agree
2	I think that government policies support entrepreneurship	5	9	50	128	123	1300	1575	82%	Agree
3	The government will promote thriving businesses	2	8	50	125	130	1318	1575	83%	Agree
4	The government will promote environmentally friendly businesses	2	6	52	120	135	1325	1575	84%	Strongly agree
5	There is good demand for environmentally friendly products during market changes in consumer tastes	3	7	54	116	135	1318	1575	83%	Agree
6	There is good demand for environmentally friendly products during market changes in consumer preferences	3	10	51	103	148	1328	1575	84%	Strongly agree
Shoes Total									7906	
Shoes Ideal									9450	
Variable Average Favourable Market Conditions									83%	

Source: (Author's Processed Data, 2023)

From the results of data regarding variables Favourable market conditions in table 4.4, it can be described as follows.

1. I can easily get a loan for my startup.

Respondents' responses about how I can easily get a loan for a startup resulted in a percentage of 83% in the agree category. This indicates that respondents can easily get loans for startups.

2. I think that government policies support entrepreneurship.

Respondents' responses regarding I think that government policies support entrepreneurship resulted in a percentage of 82% in the agree category. This indicates that respondents think government policies support entrepreneurship.

3. The government will promote thriving businesses.

Respondents' responses regarding the government's promotion of growing businesses resulted in a percentage of 83% in the agreement category. This indicates that respondents ensure that the government will promote growing businesses.

4. The government will promote environmentally friendly businesses.

Respondents' responses regarding the government's promotion of environmentally friendly businesses resulted in a percentage of 84% in the strongly agreed category. This indicates that respondents agree that the government will promote environmentally friendly businesses.

5. There is good demand for environmentally friendly products during market changes in consumer tastes.

Respondents' responses regarding the existence of good demand for environmentally friendly products during market changes according to consumers resulted in a percentage of 83% in the agreed category. This indicates that respondents are aware of good demand for environmentally friendly products during market changes in consumer tastes.

6. There is good demand for environmentally friendly products during market changes in consumer preferences.

Respondents' responses regarding the existence of good demand for environmentally friendly products during market changes in consumer preferences resulted in a preference of 84% in the strongly agreed category. This indicates that respondents are aware of good demand for environmentally friendly products during market changes in consumer preferences.

Based on the provisions of the score interpretation continuum line, it can be seen that the average percentage of the variable Favourable Market Conditions was 83% with the agreed category being in the range of 68% - 84%. So it can be concluded based on the results of this interpretation Favourable Market Conditions influence perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship.

Figure 4: Favorable Market Conditions Continuum Line

Source: (Author's Processed Data, 2023)

3.5 Analysis Partial Least Square

3.5.1 Measurement Model Analysis (Outer Model)

In this research, testing of the measurement model (outer model) the aim is to see whether the research instruments used in this study are valid and reliable. Evaluation Router model with reflexive indicators there are 3 criteria, namely convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability. Testing was carried out using software SmartPLS 4.0 with variables Eco-friendly people (EFP), Green Marketing Factors (GMF), Changing Consumer Behavior (CCB), Favorable Market Conditions (FMC), Perceptions of Sustainable Entrepreneurship (PSE). The following are the results of the test outer model towards this research.

Figure 5: Outer Model

Source: (Author's Processed Data Using SmartPLS, 2023)

3.5.2 Convergent Validity

There are two value criteria that are evaluated in convergent validity, namely value loading factor and value average variance inflation factor (AVE) (Hamid & Anwar, 2019). The value loading factor of an indicator is expected to be more than 0.7 to show that an indicator in a variable has convergent validity.

Table 5: Outer Loading Test Results

	CCB	EFP	FMC	GMF	WHY
CCB 1	0.830				
CCB 2	0.807				
CCB 3	0.826				
CCB 4	0.837				
CCB 5	0.824				
CCB 6	0.743				
EFP 1		0.731			
EFP 2		0.795			
EFP 3		0.776			
EFP 4		0.855			
EFP 5		0.787			
EFP 6		0.716			
FMC 1			0.768		
FMC 2			0.788		
FMC 3			0.729		
FMC 4			0.760		
FMC 5			0.795		
FMC 6			0.774		
GMF 1				0.741	
GMF 2				0.820	
GMF 3				0.814	
GMF 4				0.798	
GMF 5				0.789	
GMF 6				0.768	
WHY 1					0.764
WHY 2					0.846
WHY 3					0.856
WHY 4					0.850

Source: (Author's Processed Data Using SmartPLS, 2023)

Based on output outer loading it can be seen that the results loading factor shows that all indicators meet convergent validity, this finding is proven by the absence of indicator items that have value loading factor < 0.7. Meanwhile, on value average variance extracted (AVE) is expected to have a value of more than 0.5 to show that all indicators in the same variable have sufficient convergent validity (Indrawati, 2015). So it can be concluded that each instrument from the indicators in this research variable has been said to be valid and can be continued to the next stage. The following are the AVE test results in table 4.7.

Table 6: Average variance extracted (AVE) Test Results

Variables	AVE	\sqrt{AVE}
CCB	0.659	0.812
EFP	0.605	0.778
FMC	0.592	0.769
GMF	0.622	0.789
WHY	0.688	0.829

Source: (Author's Processed Data Using SmartPLS, 2023)

3.5.3 Discriminant Validity

At this stage there are two value criteria that will be evaluated, namely value Fornell – Larcker criterion, cross loading, ratio heterotrait – monotrait (HTMT) was used to test discriminant validity. The correlation value between the constructs of each variable in this study can be said to be valid or reliable if the correlation value is > 0.70 and < 0.90 for the ratio heterotrait – monotrait (HTMT) and the AVE root value of the construct is greater than the correlation between variables and other variables for Fornell – Larcker criterion (Hamid & Anwar, 2019). In Table 4.8

Table 7: Results of the Fornell – Larcker Criterion Validity Test

	CCB	EFP	FMC	GMF	WHY
CCB	0.812				
EFP	0.681	0.778			
FMC	0.652	0.621	0.769		
GMF	0.729	0.746	0.688	0.789	
WHY	0.697	0.720	0.667	0.740	0.830

Source: (Author's Processed Data Using SmartPLS, 2023)

Based on Table 4.8, it can be seen that the root of AVE in each construct has a value that is greater than the correlation between existing constructs. Based on this, it can be concluded that this research variable meets the requirements for discriminant validity (Hamid & Anwar, 2019).

Table 8: Cross Loading Validity Test Results

	CCB	EFP	FMC	GMF	WHY
CCB 1	0.830	0.596	0.589	0.619	0.599
CCB 2	0.807	0.553	0.548	0.590	0.547
CCB 3	0.826	0.564	0.550	0.594	0.589
CCB 4	0.837	0.545	0.510	0.569	0.542
CCB 5	0.824	0.579	0.511	0.620	0.615
CCB 6	0.743	0.470	0.463	0.554	0.490
EFP 1	0.516	0.731	0.478	0.600	0.574
EFP 2	0.534	0.795	0.481	0.618	0.643
EFP 3	0.544	0.776	0.469	0.601	0.518
EFP 4	0.567	0.855	0.519	0.612	0.603
EFP 5	0.507	0.787	0.488	0.514	0.504

EFP 6	0.509	0.716	0.464	0.519	0.490
FMC 1	0.534	0.471	0.768	0.562	0.564
FMC 2	0.503	0.500	0.788	0.545	0.499
FMC 3	0.485	0.417	0.729	0.464	0.420
FMC 4	0.472	0.417	0.760	0.452	0.438
FMC 5	0.499	0.481	0.795	0.526	0.541
FMC 6	0.511	0.559	0.774	0.597	0.578
GMF 1	0.508	0.544	0.514	0.741	0.589
GMF 2	0.640	0.666	0.596	0.820	0.647
GMF 3	0.589	0.606	0.538	0.814	0.611
GMF 4	0.581	0.600	0.541	0.798	0.580
GMF 5	0.597	0.572	0.529	0.789	0.513
GMF 6	0.529	0.529	0.530	0.768	0.545
WHY 1	0.459	0.498	0.452	0.535	0.764
WHY 2	0.574	0.595	0.547	0.608	0.846
WHY 3	0.658	0.636	0.619	0.647	0.856
WHY 4	0.601	0.646	0.578	0.656	0.850

Source: (Author's Processed Data Using SmartPLS, 2023)

Based on Table 8 showing the results of the discriminant validity test by looking at the cross loading values that have been tested previously via SmartPLS software, it can be seen that all the 28 indicators in this research have produced cross loading values > 0.7. Therefore, all indicators in this research have met the requirements for discriminant validity (Hamid & Anwar, 2019).

Table 9: Discriminant Validity Test Results HTMT

	CCB	EFP	FMC	GMF	WHY
CCB					
EFP	0.770				
FMC	0.738	0.711			
GMF	0.820	0.847	0.781		
WHY	0.789	0.826	0.763	0.849	

Source: (Author's Processed Data Using SmartPLS, 2023)

Based on Table 8, it can be seen that the heterotrait – monotrait ratio (HTMT) in this study has a value of <0.90, which means that the items measured are different from each other. So it can be concluded that all construct indicators in this research are valid and have met the requirements for discriminant validity (Hamid & Anwar, 2019).

3.5.4 Reliability Test

In analytical methods Partial Least Squares Path Modeling (PLS-SEM), the construct validity test stage can be carried out by looking at the values composite reliability and Cronbach alpha > 0.70 (Hamid & Anwar, 2019). Table 4.11 below shows the results of the reliability tests that have been processed by SmartPLS 4.0.

Table 10: Reliability Test Results

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)
CCB	0.896	0.900	0.921
EFP	0.869	0.874	0.902
FMC	0.863	0.868	0.897
GMF	0.879	0.881	0.908
WHY	0.849	0.858	0.898

Source: (Author's Processed Data Using SmartPLS, 2023)

In this research, reliability testing was carried out with the aim of finding out and proving how accurate, consistent and precise an instrument is in measuring a variable. In this research, reliability testing was carried out by looking at the value of Cronbach's alpha with a minimum value of > 0.7 and composite reliability value with a minimum value of > 0.7 . Based on Table 4.11 above, it can be seen that Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values show values > 0.7 , which means that all variables have a high level of reliability. So it can be concluded that all indicators in this study have met the requirements of the reliability test, which means that all indicators can be said to be accurate, consistent and precise in measuring variables.

3.5.5 Model Structural (Inner Model)

The structural model (inner model) aims to identify and see the relationship between construct variables (exogenous and endogenous) in a study. In the structural model (inner model) there are several items that are criteria for assessment, including the R Square, F Square, Q Square and t statistics tests. Structural model measurements were carried out using SmartPLS software.

Figure 5: Inner Model

Source: (Author's Processed Data Using SmartPLS, 2023)

Determination Test (R-Square)

In this research testing Coefficient of Determination (R-Square) is carried out with the aim of measuring the level of variation in changes in the independent variable towards the dependent variable (Hamid and Anwar, 2019).

Table 11: R-Square Analysis Results

	R-square	R-square adjusted
WHY	0.654	0.650

Source: (Author's Processed Data Using SmartPLS, 2023)

The independent variable has an influence of 65.4% on perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship as evidenced by the R-Square coefficient of 0.654.

Effect Size (F-Square)

In this research, the f-square test was carried out with the aim of finding out whether a model has a good value or can describe how much exogenous variables influence endogenous variables in the structure. A value of 0.02 represents a weak influence, 0.15 represents a moderate influence and 0.35 represents a strong influence in the structural model (Kante et al., 2018). In Table 4.13 F-Square Test Results which have been tested using SmartPLS software.

Table 12: F-Square Test Results

	CCB	EFP	FMC	GMF	WHY
CCB					0.044
EFP					0.085
FMC					0.048
GMF					0.065
WHY					

Source: (Author's Processed Data Using SmartPLS, 2023)

Based on Table 4.13, it can be seen that the relationship between the variables changing consumer behavior, eco-friendly people, favorable market conditions, and green marketing factors on the variable perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship has an f-square value close to 0.02, which explains that this value has a weak influence.

Predictive Relevance (Q-Square)

In this research, the Q-Square () test was carried out to describe predictive relevance, namely the suitability of the structural relevance of the model. This test can be carried out through redundancy-based blindfolding calculations, where if the value < 0 it means that the independent latent variable is less able to predict the existing construct. The Q-Square test categories are 0.02, 0.015 and 0.35, which respectively mean weak, moderate and strong. Table 4.14 below shows the results of the Q-Square values which have been tested using SmartPLS software.

Table 13: Q-Square Test Results

Variable	predict	RMSE	THERE IS
WHY	0.626	0.619	0.444

Source: (Author's Processed Data Using SmartPLS, 2023)

Based on Table 4.14, it can be seen that the variable perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship (Y) has a value > 0.35 , meaning the dependent variable can predict the existing construct.

Hypothesis testing

In this research, to find out whether it has an effect or not, it can be seen from the T statistics and P value. The T table used in this research is 1.64 because the hypothesis proposed uses a positive direction of influence or uses a P value with a significance level of 0.05 or 5%. The criteria for accepting a hypothesis can be seen directly when the T statistic value $> P$ value < 0.05 and the original sample value is positive. The following are the output results from the significance test via the bootstrapping menu.

Table 14: Hypothesis Test Results

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
CCB -> PSE	0.195	0.194	0.077	2.550	0.011
EFP -> PSE	0.272	0.273	0.094	2.910	0.004
FMC -> PSE	0.187	0.192	0.066	2.852	0.004
GMF -> PSE	0.266	0.262	0.097	2.737	0.006

Source: (Author's Processed Data Using SmartPLS, 2023)

From Table 4.15 above it can be seen that:

- 1 The changing consumer behavior variable on perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship has a statistical T value of $2,550 > 1.64$ and a P value of $0.011 < 0.05$ and the original sample has a positive value of 0.195, meaning that the changing consumer behavior variable has a positive and significant effect on perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship.
- 2 The eco-friendly people variable on perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship has a statistical T value of $2,910 > 1.64$ and a P value of $0.004 < 0.05$ and the original sample has a positive value of 0.272, meaning the eco-friendly people variable has a positive and significant effect on perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship.
- 3 The favorable market conditions variable on perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship has a statistical T value of $2,852 > 1.64$ and a P value of $0.004 < 0.05$ and the original sample has a positive value of 0.187, meaning that the favorable market conditions variable has a positive and significant effect on perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship.

The green marketing factors variable on perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship has a statistical T value of $2,737 > 1.64$ and a P value of $0.006 < 0.05$ and the original sample has a positive value of 0.266, meaning the green marketing factors variable has a positive and significant effect on perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Discussion of Research Results

This research delves into the perceptions of prospective young entrepreneurs regarding sustainable entrepreneurship in the city of Bandung. The information gathered in this research is derived from a distributed questionnaire comprising 28 statement items, reaching a total of 315 respondents among Master of Business Administration students in Bandung City. The male respondents constituted the majority, accounting for 51.7%, as opposed to female respondents at 48.3%. Data processing utilized SPSS and SmartPLS. The age distribution among Master's students majoring in business administration in Bandung City reveals that 54% fall within the age range of 21-25 years, while those aged 26-30 years constitute 31.4%, 31-35 years at 10.5%, and those above 35 years at 4.1%. Respondents from various universities in Bandung City indicate dominance by Telkom University at 36%, followed by Bandung Institute of Technology at 23.8%, Padjadjaran University at 20.6%, and Parahyangan Catholic University at 19.4%. In terms of occupations, student respondents comprise the majority at 46.7%, followed by employees at 36.2%, civil servants at 6.7%, self-employed at 5.7%, and other occupations at 4.8%.

Hypotheses:

- H1: The research reveals that eco-friendly individuals exert a positive and significant influence of 27.2% on perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship. This aligns with prior research indicating a positive relationship between eco-friendly behavior and sustainable entrepreneurship, particularly among Master's students majoring in business administration who exhibit environmentally friendly practices and interest in environmental activities (Soomro, B.A., K. Almahdi, H. & Shah, N. 2021).
- H2: The research indicates that green marketing factors wield a positive and significant impact of 26.6% on perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship. This corresponds with earlier research establishing a positive relationship between green marketing factors and sustainable entrepreneurship. These factors contribute to heightened awareness among respondents regarding environmentally friendly products and labels (Soomro, B.A., K. Almahdi, H. & Shah, N. 2021).
- H3: Changing consumer behavior is found to have a significant and positive effect of 19.5% on perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship. This mirrors previous research demonstrating a positive association between changing consumer behavior and sustainable entrepreneurship (Soomro, B.A., K. Almahdi, H. & Shah, N. 2021). Such behavioral changes indicate a shift toward more environmentally friendly products, reinforcing sustainable entrepreneurship and motivating eco-friendly businesses.
- H4: Favorable market conditions demonstrate a positive and significant impact of 18.7% on perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship. This aligns with prior research highlighting a positive relationship between favorable market conditions and sustainable entrepreneurship (Soomro, B.A., K. Almahdi, H. & Shah, N. 2021). The absence of a green marketing concept has posed challenges to sustainable entrepreneurship in the market.

Government policies supporting sustainable entrepreneurship through funding or investor promotion can create favorable market conditions.

5. CONCLUSION

Drawing conclusions from the testing and data analysis conducted with responses collected from 315 respondents via Google Form, the following points are emphasized regarding the perceptions of prospective young entrepreneurs toward sustainable entrepreneurship in the city of Bandung. Firstly, all research variables fall within the agree category, with average percentages for eco-friendly people at 80%, green marketing factors at 82%, changing consumer behavior at 81%, favorable market conditions at 83%, and perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship at 83%. Secondly, based on hypothesis testing, eco-friendly individuals, green marketing factors, changing consumer behavior, and favorable market conditions all exhibit positive and significant effects on perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship. These findings align with previous research and suggest a strong influence of eco-friendly behaviors, marketing strategies, consumer attitudes, and market conditions on the perceptions of sustainable entrepreneurship.

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